

EFFECT OF GLYTSIRRIZINIC ACID SALT ON WHEAT GROWTH IN WHEAT GRAIN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6059413>

Xusanova Z. B, Djuraev T.A

*Student of Gulistan State University, 3rd year, "Agronomy".
 Teacher of "Chemistry" department of Gulistan State University*

The metabolic process is also related to the state of micronutrient presence in cells and tissues. In studies, the effect of the trace element Zn on metabolism and plant productivity is noted separately. Accordingly, the use of GK-Zn complex in the study is considered promising to increase crop yields in agriculture by optimizing the level of activity in the growth and development of wheat. Various exogenous compounds are used to stimulate plant growth and induce resistance to abiotic factors [1,2,3]. For example, the application of solutions of ascorbic acid and kinetin in certain concentrations through plant leaves has contributed to plant growth [4]. The monoammonium salt of glycyrrhizinic acid can promote the germination of cotton seeds [5]. Glycyrrhizinic acid compounds have been reported to have multifunctional properties. Some salts of glycyrrhizic acid have been reported to regulate the growth and development of wheat [6]. During the next series of laboratory studies, the concentration of glycyrrhizic acid with Zn²⁺ + (GK-Zn) depends on the concentration (0.5-100 μM) of germination of wheat variety "Krasnodar" in the laboratory, photosynthetic activity, chlorophyll content, root germination activity and chlorophyll count was studied.

Influence of GK-Zn complex on germination of grain of Krasnodar wheat variety (M ± m)

Table 1

Experiment options	Growth rate(%)	(The length of the grass(мм))	(Root length(мм))	(Weight of biomass in wet state(gr))	Weight of biomass in dry state(gr)
(controlled distilled water)	84,1	13,13±0,55	10,04±0,4 3	2,004±0,3 2	0,201±0,0 3
ГK-Zn (5×10 ⁻⁷ M)	92,1**	14,54±0,5 4	10,98±0,31 *	2,011±0,12 *	0,208±0,0 1*

ГK-Zn (1×10-6M)	95,2**	18,34±0,3 3**	14,13±0,45 **	2,213±0,2 2**	0,234±0,0 2**
ГK-Zn (1×10-5M)	91,3**	16,02±0,41 **	14,04±0,6 4**	2,105±0,17 **	0,228±0,0 2**
ГK-Zn (5×10-5M)	90,1**	13,65±0,3 7*	11,12±0,23 **	2,065±0,1 3*	0,219±0,0 5**
ГK-Zn (1×10-4M)	88,5*	13,02±0,2 8*	10,34±0,5 3*	2,011±0,53 *	0,213±0,0 3*
ГK-Zn (1×10-3M)	85,8*	14,45±0,5 5**	9,43±0,54 *	2,008±0,2 3*	0,205±0,0 3*

Note: Represents the degree of statistical reliability of the difference between the values of the experimental groups relative to the control group (* - $r < 0.05$; ** - $r < 0.01$).

Under the influence of GK-Zn, the degree of germination of wheat variety "Krasnodar" in the laboratory and, in turn, the increase in root length, weight of biomass in wet and dry conditions was observed relative to control (Table 1).

Effect of GK-Zn complex on chlorophyll content in wheat green biomass. Subsequent experiments reported a significant increase in the amount of chlorophyll in the green biomass of wheat under the influence of GK-Zn complex (1-100 μM), including a maximum increase in concentration of 1 μM , ie $112.4 \pm 5.7\%$ compared to control (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Effect of GK-Zn complex (10 μM) on the amount of chlorophyll in the green biomass of wheat variety "Krasnodar". On the ordinate axis - the amount of chlorophyll (%). ** - $r < 0.05$ ($n = 3-5$) relative to the control.

It was also noted that there was a correlation between wheat grass length, root length, and chlorophyll content values.

REFERENCES:

1. Akula Ramakrishna and Gokare Aswathanarayana Ravishankar, 2011. Influence of abiotic stress signals on secondary metabolites in plants *Plant Signal Behav.* Nov 1; 6(11): 1720–1731.
2. Rehman, H., Q. Nawaz, S.M.A. Basra, I. Afzal, A. Yasmeen and F.U. Hassan, 2014. Seed priming influence on early crop growth, phenological development and yield performance of linola (*Linum usitatissimum* L.). *J. Integ. Agric.*, in press
3. Yasmeen, A., S.M.A. Basra, M. Farooq, H. Rehman, N. Hussain, H. R. Athar, 2013. Exogenous application of moringa leaf extract modulates the antioxidant enzyme system to improve wheat performance under saline conditions. *Plant Growth Regul.*, 69: 225– 233
4. Azza A.M. Mazher, Sahar M. Zaghloul, Safaa A. Mahmoud and Hanan S. Siam (2011) Stimulatory Effect of Kinetin, Ascorbic acid and Glutamic Acid on Growth and Chemical Constituents of *Codiaeum variegatum* L. *Plants. American-Eurasian J. Agric. & Environ. Sci.*, 10 (3): 318-323
5. Akhunov.A.A.,Golibenko Z., Dalimov D.N., Abdurashidova N.A., Mustakimova E.Ch., Ibragimov F.A., Akbarova G.O.(2004) Diglycyrrinats as regulators of grows cotton. *Chemical Natural Compounds*. N1. Pp.58-61.
6. Kushiev Kh.H., Karomat Ismailova A., Dalimov N. (2013) Regulation of development of a rust of wheat using physiologically active compounds. *European sciences and technology*. Germany, 2013. Pp.71-76.